

Deliverable 3.1

Summary Report on socio-economic and ecological data and indicators

10 April 2025

Author: CMCC Foundation

MOIRAI

www.moirai-project.eu

Multiscale Ocean models and Information for climate Risk Assessment and Impact mitigation.

Research and Innovation Action under EC Horizon Europe
Grant Agreement no. 101180994

Project coordinator:
ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION (NTUA),
Greece

Deliverable 3.1
Title of the Deliverable

Start date of project: 01 November 2024
Due date of deliverable: 30 April 2025

Duration: 42 months
Actual submission date: 30 April 2025

Lead beneficiary for preparing the deliverable: CMCC Foundation

Authors: Vibe Schourup-Kristensen (AU), Paola Tanguy (CMCC), Matteo Mazzarano (CMCC), Chiara Trozzo (CMCC), Giulia Gallucio (CMCC), Vera Sidorenko (AWI), Alexey Androsov (AWI), Sebastian Villasante (USC), Adrian Sobral Lores (USC), Sofia Estevez Rivadulla (USC), Maria Teresa Moreira Vilar (USC), Jeroen Steenbeek (EII), Marta Coll (CSIC), Till Rasmussen (DMI)

Version	DATE	CHANGE RECORDS	Responsible
0.1	12.02.2025	Template	EurOcean
0.2	03.04.2025	Draft submitted to WP lead	Deliverable lead CMCC.
0.3	04.04.2025	Reviewed deliverable	WP lead Marie Maar
0.4	10.04.2025	Final version submitted to Coordination Team after revision based on WP lead review	Deliverable lead CMCC
1.0	20.04.2025	Reviewed Final version submitted to EC	Coordination team

DISSEMINATION LEVEL		
PU	Public, fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
Classified R-UE/EU-R	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified C-UE/EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444	
Classified S-UE/EU-S	EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444	

DELIVERABLE TYPE		
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	x
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
DMP	Data management plan	
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	
SECURITY:	Deliverables related to security issues	
OTHER:	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Coastal marine environments are affected by multiple stressors, such as climate change and chemical pollution, while also being important for e.g. fisheries, renewable energy development and recreational activities. To support sustainable use of the seas, ensure good status of marine ecosystems, and comply with European legislation, it is necessary to monitor and assess the status of marine environments. One tool is ecosystem, climatic and socio-economic indicators.

To support the further development of relevant marine indicators in the MOIRAI project, we carried out literature reviews focusing on the current use of indicators. The focus of the literature review was on indicators of ecosystem status, climate change and socio-economic factors. Indeed, given the strong interplay between coastal marine ecosystems and human activities, the integration of socio-economic indicators, in combination with ecosystem indicators, can improve our understanding of coastal marine environment dynamics, and provide a more holistic perspective.

The literature reviews showed that indicators are increasingly used. Marine ecosystem indicators have been predominantly applied in European waters, and especially benthic biodiversity and eutrophication indicators have been used. In recent years, an effort towards holistic assessments of marine ecosystem status has taken place, leading to comprehensive tools for ecosystem assessment. With regards to socio-economic indicators, research on evaluating climate impacts on infrastructure, in particular coastal erosion and sea level rise, is well developed, but gaps on transport or renewable energy supply were revealed. Other fields of study, such as living resources and tourism, are less prevalent, while research on non-living resources is quasi-absent. The literature review also demonstrated a strong focus on developing economies, while research on developed regions, including the Mediterranean, that are the focus of the MOIRAI project, is lacking. However, both ecosystem and socio-economic indicators are less developed around commercial fish species and aquaculture, pointing to a gap that the MOIRAI project can aim to fulfill.

Despite progress in the development of climate synthetic indicators, especially the integration of socio-economic data with ecological and physical factors lacks standardization, which hinders long-term monitoring and actionability. The MOIRAI project will work towards indicators that take physical, chemical, biological, socio-economic and climate factors into account, and thus be able to support better-informed decision making and enhance coastal resilience and sustainable management.

Acknowledgements:

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. The European Union cannot be held responsible for them.

Add acknowledgement to other projects or other major contributors to the activity/deliverable (e.g., ship time, RI infrastructure, or use of data from other projects.)

Table of Contents

TABLE OF CONTENTS	3
1. INTRODUCTION	6
1.1 LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORKS FOR COASTAL MANAGEMENT	6
1.2 DIVERSITY OF INDICATORS FOR COASTAL MANAGEMENT.....	6
1.3 MARINE ECOSYSTEM AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC INDICATORS.....	7
1.4 LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY AND ASSOCIATED GAPS.....	8
1.5 INDICATOR DEVELOPMENT IN MOIRAI	9
2. METHODS	10
2.1 DEFINITIONS	10
2.2 INDICATORS FOR ASSESSMENT OF ECOSYSTEM STATUS	10
2.3 SOCIO-ECONOMIC AND CLIMATIC INDICATORS	12
2.4 LIFE CYCLE ANALYSIS AND INDICATORS	14
3. RESULTS.....	16
3.1 LITERATURE REVIEW OF INDICATORS FOR MARINE ECOSYSTEM STATUS ASSESSMENT	16
3.1.1 <i>Applied ecosystem indicators</i>	16
3.1.2 <i>Composite indices for marine ecosystem assessment</i>	18
3.1.3 <i>Grouping marine ecosystem indicators based on topic</i>	22
3.1.4 <i>Ecosystem indicators in European conventions and directives</i>	24
3.2 SOCIO-ECONOMIC AND CLIMATIC INDICATORS	25
3.2.1 <i>Sectoral distribution of articles</i>	25
3.2.2 <i>Distribution of climate indicator-related articles over time</i>	27
3.2.3 <i>Coastal vulnerability</i>	28
3.2.4 <i>Relevance of socio-economic climate indicator-related literature over time</i>	28
3.2.5 <i>Methodologies and research approaches</i>	29
3.2.6 <i>Topic analysis</i>	29
3.3 SOCIO-ECONOMIC DATA COLLECTION	30
3.4 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LIFE CYCLE ANALYSIS AND INDICATORS.....	32
3.4.1 <i>LCA indicator: Climate change</i>	32
3.4.2 <i>LCA indicator: Marine ecotoxicity</i>	34
3.4.3 <i>LCA indicator: Marine eutrophication</i>	34
3.4.4 <i>LCA indicator: Ecosystem quality</i>	35

3.4.5 LCA indicator: Land use or “Seabed use”	37
3.4.6 LCA indicator: Human health.....	38
3.4.7 New LCA indicator: Depletion of biotic resources.....	38
4. DISCUSSION.....	39
4.1 CURRENT USE OF INDICATORS.....	39
4.2 NUMERICAL MODELS AS TOOLS FOR MARINE ECOSYSTEM INDICATORS	40
4.3 MOIRAI MODELS AND INDICATOR WORK	42
4.3.1 The Arctic.....	42
4.3.2 The North Sea	43
4.3.3 Mediterranean Sea.....	43
5. CONCLUDING REMARKS.....	44
6. REFERENCES	45

Table of Figures

FIGURE 3-1: NUMBER OF STUDIES ON ECOSYSTEM STATUS INDICATORS FROM THE SCOPUS SEARCH. THE COLORS DENOTE THE TYPES OF INDICATORS USED IN THE STUDIES.	16
FIGURE 3-2: REGIONAL SEA FOCUS OF THE STUDIES IN THE LITERATURE REVIEW. BAR COLORS DENOTE THE YEAR OF PUBLICATIONS.	17
FIGURE 3-3: INDICATOR GROUPING IN THE LITERATURE REVIEW. THE GROUP “PELAGIC: LTL” DENOTE THE PELAGIC LOWER TROPHIC LEVEL INDICATORS. STUDIES IN THE GROUP “OTHER” MAKE USE OF MACROALGAE, CORAL REEF, CETACEANS, MARINE LITTER AND BIRDS, RESPECTIVELY.	18
FIGURE 3-4: INDICATORS GROUP BY TOPIC	23
FIGURE 3-5: OVERVIEW OF THE INDICATORS USED MOST FREQUENTLY IN THE STUDIES OF THE LITERATURE REVIEW. COLORS DENOTE THE TOPIC INTO WHICH THE INDICATOR WAS GROUPED.....	23
FIGURE 3-6: DISTRIBUTION OF SECTORS IN THE REVIEWED ARTICLES	26
FIGURE 3-7: TRENDS IN PUBLISHED PAPERS.....	27
FIGURE 3-8: SUM OF CITATIONS PER YEAR	28
FIGURE 3-9: LDA TOPIC MODELING RESULT.....	30

Table of Tables

TABLE 2-1: STEPS OF ECOSYSTEM INDICATOR LITERATURE REVIEW 12

TABLE 2-2: STEPS OF LITERATURE REVIEW OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC AND CLIMATIC INDICATORS..... 14

TABLE 3-1: COMPOSITE INDICES APPLIED IN MORE THAN ONE STUDY IN THE LITERATURE REVIEW. 20

1. Introduction

The coastal environment is affected by cumulative stressors, such as warming, eutrophication and pollution with hazardous substances, from the marine, land and atmospheric environments (IPBES, 2024). At the same time, coastal areas, often densely populated, rely on the sea for socio-economic purposes, such as fisheries, aquaculture, renewable energy development, tourism and recreational activities (Filho et al. 2022). Coastal nations are thus particularly vulnerable to the multifaceted consequences of climate change, including sea-level rise, erosion, flooding, and extreme weather events. It is thus important to carry out robust and informed decision-making to mitigate its effects, and to manage the health of the coastal ecosystems while also taking human needs and wants into account.

1.1 Legislative frameworks for coastal management

The European Union (EU) Water Framework Directive (WFD, 2000/60/EC) and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, 2008/56/EC, European Commission 2008) require ecosystem-focused management of the marine environment, with the goal of a sustainable use of the seas. EU Member States are thus required to monitor, assess, protect and improve the status of their seas to obtain Good Environmental Status (GES, Smith et al. 2016). The implementation of the MSFD in shared water bodies relies on regional co-operations, such as OSPAR (the North-East Atlantic), HELCOM (the Baltic Sea), the Barcelona Convention (the Mediterranean) and the Bucharest Convention (Black Sea). Complementary legislation exists around the world, e.g. the Oceans Act in the USA, Canada and Australia, and the National Water Act in South Africa.

1.2 Diversity of indicators for coastal management

Effectively addressing these challenges and evaluating the state of marine ecosystems is a major challenge for management (Pinna et al., 2023): one tool is ecological and socio-economic indicators. Due to the large variability of marine ecosystems in time and space, indicators for assessing the ecological status of the sea vary depending on location and focus of the study at hand (Dale and Beyeler, 2001). Indicators may be made up of information regarding physical factors, such temperature and salinity (Rani et al., 2019),

biogeochemical and biological factors, such as pH, oxygen and biodiversity (Troast et al., 2020), or human factors, such as exploitation and use of marine resources. Further, a shift towards holistic assessments that integrate both climate and socio-economic indicators has been made possible thanks to satellite observations, climate models, and other technological advancements. Climate synthetic indicators leverage such advancements by mixing available specific data to identify and predict vulnerability, as well as forecasting risks on the multifaceted exposure to climate change of coastal communities.

1.3 Marine ecosystem and socio-economic indicators

A good indicator of marine ecosystem health must be measurable, sensitive and specific (Link et al., 2010). Measurability implies that indicator data exists, is available, and preferably relatively easy to obtain, following e.g. the FAIR principles (Gregoire et al., 2021). Further, an indicator must be sensitive to change, while responding specifically to pressures they are designed to detect, and not to other pressures (Shin et al., 2018). However, identifying change requires knowledge of the reference state, something that can be especially challenging in the rapidly changing, diverse, and often remote and inaccessible marine environment (Trifinova et al., 2022). Further, to put current changes into perspective, long time series of key ocean variables are important to understand the variability of the ocean on a range of time scales (Pitois et al., 2022). While the reference state is important as baseline knowledge, environmental targets defined in relation to the reference and current states are likewise key in marine management (Borja et al., 2012). The definition of targets is further complicated by nonlinear biological responses (Boldt et al., 2021) and interactions between single indicators and between trophic levels (Kadin et al., 2019).

In terms of management, clear, concise and consistent ecosystem health indicators and targets are important as they make the impact of human pressures on the ecosystem clear for the public, hence increasing understanding of mitigation measures (Bryndum-Buchholz et al., 2025). This becomes increasingly important as human pressures in the

coastal environment are changing, e.g. offshore wind farms (Wawrzynkowski et al., 2025). However, while consistency is important, knowledge and human pressures are changing over time, leading to changes in e.g. targets for GES. While large effort has been made in the development of consistent and specific indicators (e.g. HELCOM, 2013) as well as holistic tools (Borja et al., 2016), currently, a standardized set of indicators for the holistic assessment of climate change impacts on coastal ecosystems and the subsequent socio-economic consequences remain elusive. A recent review of the literature (Cruz-Ramírez et al., 2024) highlighted the diversity of approaches used to evaluate coastal vulnerability, revealing inconsistencies in the selection and weighting of variables employed. However, the work does not provide a standardization of literature with respect to sectors of relevance. This lack of standardization hinders effective cross-study comparisons, limits the ability to track changes over time and geographic locations, and complicates the development of effective mitigation and adaptation strategies.

1.4 Life Cycle Assessment methodology and associated gaps

In the field of environmental assessment, the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology has no clear approach to evaluate impacts on marine and oceanic ecosystems. Langlois et al. (2014) have made efforts to incorporate new impact categories related to sea use. These new categories consider the impacts of human activities, such as seabed destruction, the introduction of invasive species, the extraction of biotic resources, habitat loss, the creation of artificial habitats, noise, and turbidity. De Luca Peña et al. (2024) developed an innovative methodology that links life cycle impact categories with effects on ecosystem services. Additionally, they propose new characterization factors specific to the study area, allowing these impacts to be monetized and aggregated at the endpoint level. Langlois et al. (2014) also proposed a new impact category related to the depletion of biotic resources due to fishing activities.

When analyzing the integration of ecosystem services with LCA methodology, it becomes evident that further integration is needed to facilitate the connection between certain LCA categories and specific ecosystem services (VanderWilde & Newell, 2021; Alejandro

et al., 2019; De Souza et al., 2018). The scarcity of studies in this field highlights the importance of continued research to develop approaches that adequately address these impacts and improve environmental sustainability.

1.5 Indicator development in MOIRAI

The ocean is, and for the foreseeable future will continue to be, affected by climate change and other human pressures, which will continue to affect marine ecosystems, and the ecosystem services they provide, and the blue economy. The MOIRAI project aims to provide the next generation of regional-coastal physical and biogeochemical climate models for the European Seas. The specific focus of the model development is on the European Arctic, the North Sea and the Mediterranean Sea. To build and enhance resilience within these social-ecological systems, a goal of MOIRAI is to develop reliable and complimentary indicators of the ocean state with regards to ecology, socio-economy and climate. This work will in turn support the sustainable management of coastal areas and decision-making processes through the decision-support system tool REASSHORE. To support the development of indicators within the MOIRAI project, we here provide systematic literature reviews of the current use of indicators to evaluate the status of the marine environment, as well as climate change and socio-economic indicators for coastal vulnerability assessments. The report examines various indicator types, methodologies, and data sources, with a special focus on identifying the most used variables and exploring their strengths and weaknesses. It aims to address the critical need for well-defined, comprehensive, and consistently applied indicators to support scientific research, policy formulation, and effective coastal management practices, drawing lessons from past studies to improve methodology and data integration. The report will also explore the role of decision support systems (DSS) in the application of these indicators to support informed decision-making.

2. Methods

2.1 Definitions

An indicator is a measurable variable, providing information about the state of a system in relation to specific target criteria, thus making it possible to quantify and monitor change. A marine ecosystem indicator can be simpler (e.g. chlorophyll concentration) or more complex (e.g. water quality). Likewise, a socio-economic indicator can capture key dimensions of human and economic systems, from simple variables, such as employment or income levels, to more complex metrics (e.g. measuring the resilience of a coastal community). Indicators aim at providing an assessment of a complex area through a limited number of variables (Turnhout et al., 2007), and are thus means for communication between researchers, policy makers and the public.

An index combines multiple indicators to provide a comprehensive quantitative single score of the state of an ecosystem or socio-economic system. An index measured and calculated several times over space or time can be applied as an indicator to effectively communicate change to policy makers.

2.2 Indicators for assessment of ecosystem status

To perform a literature review on indicators used to assess the status of marine ecosystems we used the bibliographic database Scopus to identify relevant peer-reviewed scientific articles in English. The search was carried out on the 6th of February 2025. SCOPUS is a large curated and well-indexed database, entailing studies with a global coverage (Baas et al., 2020), thus providing high-quality data for our study. The initial broader search included the search term ("*marine ecosystem status*") AND ("*indicator*"), including titles, abstracts and keywords of scientific articles in the database. The search was done without restrictions in time or geography but was limited to scientific articles in the categories "Environmental science", "Earth and Planetary Science" and "Multidisciplinary", as these categories were deemed relevant for the focus of our study.

This search query resulted in a list of 702 scientific articles. Titles were screened to only include studies with the focus on ecosystem science of marine and transitional waters, including fjords, estuaries and lagoons, and studies which had an indicator-focused goal. This secondary screening left a list of 307 studies. From this list, abstracts were screened to include only studies in which indicators were used to assess the status of ecosystems in the marine environment. Consequently, studies focusing on e.g. developing new indicators and studies discussing the importance of indicators were excluded from the literature review. This final screening led to a list of 138 scientific papers (Table 2-1). The final articles were screened to determine the type of indicator used. This was first done by dividing into categories based on broad biological characteristics and sampling location, such as benthic indicators and pelagic indicators. This was done to understand which habitats and biological groups were mainly used in indicator work. Secondly, the indicators were categorized based on the issue they aimed to address, e.g. biodiversity, eutrophication and hazardous substances. This division is not trivial, as the category biodiversity can be an indicator for external pressures such as eutrophication or hazardous substances. However, the categories do give an overview of the types of indicators used are largely similar to the categories suggested by HELCOM (2013). To increase transparency and reduce bias in selection, we as far as possible followed the ROSES guidelines of Haddaway et al. (2018), which is a further development of the PRISMA guidelines, aiming at environmental studies. ROSES provides a structured template for the through the sections of the literature review along with a flow-diagram to report the article selection process (Simplified in Table 2-1).

Table 2-1: Steps of ecosystem indicator literature review

Step	Number of articles	Notes
Database Search	702	Found from Scopus
1 st round of processing	307	Kept only articles with focus on ecosystem science of marine and transitional waters
2 nd round of processing	138	Kept only the articles that entailed applied indicators

2.3 Socio-economic and climatic indicators

The first delivery of the WP3 is a literature review on socioeconomic and climatic indicators, with the intent to provide insights into the information gap on resilience and risk exposure. The collection effort has been focused on academic articles retrieved from Scopus. Manual verification of alternatives databases such as WoS and Google scholar revealed significant overlapping results, indicating that inputs from these databases would provide limited additional value. The literature review has consisted of peer review papers that fit the description of the Thematic areas of the EU's [Blue Economy dashboard](#) and could be divided in such a way. The Blue Economy dashboard was selected as a reference framework for our analysis given its comprehensive structure and thematic classification of socio-economic activities, and MOIRAI's Europe-based case studies. Furthermore, we have only kept in the analysis papers or peer-reviewed reports that contain open-box approaches with information, for the reproducibility of their study to benefit the MOIRAI project. Black box approaches such as synthesis of different climate indicators with neural networks, machine learning have been discarded.

The literature review was based on three distinct phases:

- The first one was the collection phase, where relevant literature was collected from databases such as Scopus and Web of Science. A sequence of keywords was

generated through expert judgment during the writing phases of MOIRAI to capture a sufficiently wide sample of articles and reports that refer to synthetic indicators. We have not focused solely on socio-economic ones, but rather on the entirety of the body of literature of climate indicators. The body of literature referred solely to peer-reviewed articles to maintain a solid scientific background. This choice was motivated by the multiplicity of keywords for socio-economic dynamics which might have been ignored at the start of the analysis. After the collection, the relevant information of the articles collected was organized into a table. The collection referred to abstracts, authors, affiliations journals, year and keywords. Two alternative sequences of keywords were investigated: "Climate risk" AND "Coastal" AND "Index" the first time, while "Climate" AND "RISK" AND "Coastal" AND "Index" the second time. In total, we found more than 800 papers.

- The second phase was the revision phase. The initial element of the literature review required a cleaning process of hundreds of articles and then the identification of those that matter to the project. In this phase, we skimmed the raw collection for articles that referred to synthetic climate indicators with socio-economic relevance. This work was done partly by manual intervention and partly by data matching. We repeated the search for the keywords within the abstracts. This process reduced the number of articles that the sample contained. The expected rate of removal was as high as 90% due to the generality of the keywords selection. This selection approach minimized the percentage of missing articles and the number of irrelevant articles.
- The final phase consisted in identifying articles that directly addressed the thematic areas of the blue economy, organizing the available articles into the sectors, and elaborating the information in a synthetic manner. The former subphase was completed by hand, by reading each abstract and assigning a sector by proximity of issue treated.

A summary of the steps is provided in

Deliverable 3.1

Table 2-2 below.

Table 2-2: Steps of literature review of socio-economic and climatic indicators

Step	Number of articles	Notes
Database Search	808	Found from Scopus, checked on other major websites such as Google Scholar, WoS and checked for overlapping references
1 st round of processing	417	Kept articles from the previous step that contained the MOIRAI selected keywords in the keyword list or in the abstract
2 nd round of processing	67	Kept only the articles that refer to indicators that address risk or vulnerability in one of the thematic areas

The number of articles drastically reduced from 808 to 67, representing less than 10% of the initial count.

Finally, we assessed how literature has evolved in the last three decades, examining the number of papers per year and the distribution across sectors to identify the potential gaps in the literature. In addition to this analysis, we applied a topic modeling approach to reveal the thematic structure of the papers that we selected. Various studies have suggested that under expert judgment, redundancies in the topics might indicate monothematic texts. This approach (Laureate et al., 2023; Zimmermann et al., 2024) is intended to identify relevant repetition to gauge the saturation within the articles. It involves an unsupervised algorithm that identifies what are the most repeated words. Repetitions are indicative of precision in the collection of articles. In other words, if too many topics emerge in the analysis, it implies that we did not find a specific niche but multiple and possibly we did not find all relevant articles on the issue.

2.4 Life Cycle Analysis and indicators

According to the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), Life Cycle Assessment is a standardized technique for evaluating the environmental aspects and

potential impacts associated with a product, process, or service throughout its entire life cycle. This includes raw material extraction, production, distribution, use, and final disposal (Hauschild, Rosenbaum and Olsen, 2018).

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) consists of four main phases. The first is defining the goal and scope, where the purpose of the study is established, the product system is selected, functional units, system boundaries, allocation methods, and impact categories are determined. Then, in the inventory analysis, material and energy flows within the system are identified and quantified. The third phase, impact assessment, translates these data into environmental impact estimates through classification and characterization processes. Finally, life cycle interpretation allows conclusions to be drawn and recommendations to be formulated, often providing feedback to previous phases to enhance study coherence and accuracy.

Indicators can provide information about material and energy flows. These can be linked to life cycle assessment in the impact evaluation phase (LCIA) by means of characterization factors, which allow the results of the indicators to be translated into environmental impacts.

The characterization factors are determined by means of scientific and quantitative models that aim to represent as realistically as possible the cause-effect relationships of the flows that contribute to an environmental impact (Rosenbaum et al., 2017). In this section, a critical, although not systematic, review has been carried out with the aim of establishing links between the indicators and the life cycle analysis (LCA).

The objective of this section of deliverable D3.1 is to establish a relationship between the indicators identified through systematic literature review and the impact categories of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), through the search and review of scientific literature.

3. Results

3.1 Literature review of indicators for marine ecosystem status assessment

3.1.1 Applied ecosystem indicators

In our search, applied studies on indicators of marine ecosystem status started in the early 2000s, and increased sharply in 2015-2016 and 2019 (Figure 3-1). The search term “marine ecosystem status” is wording used in the European WFD (2000) and the MSFD (2008), with associated management targets and deadlines. Consequently, the peaks in publications may be related to deadlines in the WFD (2009, 2015, 2021 and 2027) and the MSFD (2016, 2022 and 2028).

Figure 3-1: Number of studies on ecosystem status indicators from the Scopus search. The colors denote the types of indicators used in the studies.

The global ocean was divided into regional seas to understand the distribution of the studies. This showed that literature in our search mainly focused on European Seas, especially the Mediterranean Sea. Further, the NW Pacific, mainly coastal waters of China, is the focus of 12% of the studies (Figure 3-2). The plot shows that research

focusing on the European Seas has been published continuously through the years, while research from the NW Pacific primarily was published in 2019 onwards. Similarly, studies from the Black Sea, the Indian Ocean and SE Asia have been published in recent years. This suggests that while European legislation is aimed at European water bodies, the methods developed here are gradually adopted by countries in other parts of the world.

Figure 3-2: Regional Sea focus of the studies in the literature review. Bar colors denote the year of publications.

While marine ecosystem indicators are increasingly based on satellite-based observations or models, which rely on mathematical description of fluxes in the marine ecosystem, traditionally, they are based on buoy- and ship-based observations in the field. Here, we divide the indicators of the literature review based on the type of sampling location (pelagic and benthic), as this has an impact on the type of ecosystem assessment carried out to decide the status of seas. Of the 138 studies in the literature review, 60 (43.5%) focused on the benthic ecosystems, such as biodiversity and heavy metal concentration in bivalves. 36 (26%) of the studies focused on the lower trophic levels of pelagic ecosystems, such as nutrient and chlorophyll concentrations, 19

studies (14%) use fish-based indicators, such as fish traits and fish stocks, while 15 studies (11%) used a combination of these categories to perform a holistic assessment. The category “Other” entails studies which apply macroalgae (4 studies) and coral reef health (4 studies) as indicators. Benthic indicators have been applied through all years, with the use rising with time, while holistic indicator assessments have only been consistently used since 2015 (Figure 3-1). The accessibility and sessile nature of benthic indicators likely contribute to them being consistently used for assessments of ecosystem status. The later, but increasing, application of holistic indicators shows how the different types of indicators have needed to be developed individually before the combined application has been possible. But the more comprehensive ecosystem assessment of holistic indicators is needed for complete assessments of ecosystems.

Figure 3-3: Indicator grouping in the literature review. The group “Pelagic: LTL” denote the pelagic lower trophic level indicators. Studies in the group “Other” make use of macroalgae, coral reef, cetaceans, marine litter and birds, respectively.

3.1.2 Composite indices for marine ecosystem assessment

Of the 138 studies included in the literature review, 84 used one or more composite indices to assess the environmental status of the marine ecosystem. Such an index is a single quantitative score for a specific location and time, calculated based on several metrics.

In total, 68 different composite indices were applied in the studies of the literature review, but only 12 were applied more than once (Table 3-1). The most used composite index was the AZTI Marine Biotic Index (AMBI, Borja et al., 2000), which was developed to assess the status of soft bottom benthic macroinvertebrate communities according to the WFD and the MSFD. The AMBI index has been applied consistently through the years in the study. Other benthic indices are the BENTIX (Simboura & Zenetos, 2002), the Benthic Opportunistic Annelids Amphipods (BO2A) Index (Dauvin & Ruellet, 2009), the Benthic Quality Index (BQI, Rosenberg et al., 2004) and the Margalef Richness Index (Margalef et al., 1973). The Shannon Diversity Index and the Pielou Evenness Index can be applied to different types of ecosystems, e.g. benthic or pelagic, but in our literature review, most studies applying these indices focused on the benthic communities. Aside from the benthic indices in the table, another 18 benthic indices were used once in the studies reviewed. These indices mentioned above focus on different aspects of biodiversity and resilience, such as species diversity, species richness, evenness, and the presence of sensitive and opportunistic species. The large number of indices developed for benthic ecosystem health supports the notion that benthic species have been more accessible for development of robust indices of the marine environment, while pelagic indices, and especially holistic indices, are more complicated and elusive in terms of monitoring and definition.

The Trophic Status Index (TRIX, Giovanardi & Vollenweider, 2004), the Eutrophication/trophic State Index (TSI, Carlson, 1977) and the Dia/Dino Index (Wasmund, 2017) all focus on the pelagic ecosystem status, by assessing the degree of eutrophication in a given water body. Another five pelagic composite indices were used once in the reviewed literature, with focus on eutrophication, zooplankton abundance and biomass, biodiversity, carbon storage and status of protected species.

Seven different composite indices for fish were used in the reviewed articles, but none were used more than once. These indices focused on fish abundance, biodiversity and species evenness, traits of fish as well as pressure from fisheries.

Table 3-1: Composite indices applied in more than one study in the literature review.

Index	Number of studies	Description
AMBI and M-AMBI (Borja et al., 2002)	33	The AZTI Marine Biotic Index, was developed to assess the ecological status of soft bottom benthic macroinvertebrate communities according to the WFD and the MSFD.
Shannon Diversity Index	16	Calculates species diversity by considering both species richness and species evenness. Can be applied to both benthic and pelagic ecosystems.
BENTIX (Simboura & Zenetos, 2002)	10	Like AMBI, the BENTIX index assesses the status of soft bottom benthic macroinvertebrate communities by using the relative occurrence of sensitive and tolerant taxa. It was developed for the WFD and MSFD.
NEAT (Borja et al., 2016)	6	The Nested Environmental status Assessment Tool integrates multiple ecosystem components, habitats and indicators to assess the overall status of marine ecosystems, both benthic and pelagic.
Trophic Status Index (TRIX) (Giovanardi & Vollenweider, 2004)	5	Classifies water bodies according to the biological productivity by calculating the trophic status of a system (oligotrophic to eutrophic), considering nutrient and chlorophyll concentration, along with oxygen saturation levels.
Margalef Richness Index (Margalef et al., 1973)	4	A measure of species richness, which takes the number of samples into account, thus standardizing the comparison of different sites.

Benthic Quality Index (BQI) (Rosenberg et al., 2004)	4	Assesses the ecological status of benthic environments based on the presence and absence of species in the benthic macroinvertebrate community. Invented for the WFD.
Eutrophication/trophic state Index (TSI) Carlson (1977)	4	Assesses the state of a water body from oligotrophic to eutrophic based on biological productivity. Takes chlorophyll and nutrient concentrations, as well as secchi depth, into account.
Pielou's Evenness Index (Pielou, 1966)	3	Based on the Shannon Diversity Index and measures the evenness of species distribution within a habitat. Useful for comparing habitats, and quantifying change over time.
Dia/Dino Index (Wasmund, 2017)	2	The diatom/dinoflagellate index was developed to assess the ecological status of the Baltic Sea according to the WFD and MSFD.
BO2A (Dauvin & Ruellet, 2009)	2	Calculates the ecological quality of a water body based on the ratio between opportunistic annelids to amphipods.
Health Status Index (HIS) Dagnina et al., (2007)	2	Uses multiple biomarkers to assess the health status of mussels in response to pollution such as nutrients or hazardous substances.

The Nested Environmental status Assessment Tool (NEAT) was used in six of the studies of the literature review. While NEAT is listed in Table 3-1, rather than being a simple composite index, it is a comprehensive tool designed to provide an integrated assessment of the status of marine ecosystems, and to support the implementation of marine policies, such as the WFD and the MSFD (Borja et al., 2016). The tool can be adapted to different marine environments and management needs, and can be applied at different spatial scales, from local to regional levels. A variety of indicators are supported by NEAT, including biodiversity, habitat quality, water quality, food webs,

commercially exploited fish and shellfish and non-indigenous species. A catalogue of more than 600 available indicators were developed and linked with NEAT to support holistic assessments of marine waters (Texeira et al., 2016). NEAT has been successfully applied in several areas including the North Sea, the Mediterranean, and the deep North Atlantic (e.g. Uusitalo et al., 2016). The software is freely available for download at www.devotes-project.eu/neat.

3.1.3 Grouping marine ecosystem indicators based on topic

The indicators used in the studies were divided into broader groups, aligning with the descriptors of the MSFD (Figure 3-4). The groups included:

- Biodiversity/ecosystem quality. This group was the largest and included 37 different benthic indicators and 13 indicators for fish biodiversity, with the most used being benthic ecological quality (Figure 3-5), which was calculated by the AMBI. Other indicators in this group included fish trophic levels, fish functional groups, functional group richness, fish biodiversity, non-indigenous species, species diversity, and species composition. Aside from fish, pelagic indicators were not well-represented in this group, though a few studies focused on cetacean and seal biodiversity.
- Eutrophication and water quality was the second largest group (Figure 3-4). This group was dominated by pelagic indicators such as nutrient, phytoplankton and oxygen concentrations. However, trophic status was calculated for both pelagic and sediment.
- The group Hazardous substances included marine litter, microplastics and heavy metals, as well as other chemical contaminants.
- The group Human pressures were dominated by fisheries and trawling pressure, but other direct human pressures included shipping and structures in the sea.
- Habitats and Ecosystem resilience are not well-defined and consequently only used nine and eight times as indicators, respectively.

- Climate change, including temperature, pH and sea ice extent were used nine times in the studies.

Figure 3-4: Indicators group by topic

Figure 3-5: Overview of the indicators used most frequently in the studies of the literature review. Colors denote the topic into which the indicator was grouped.

3.1.4 Ecosystem indicators in European conventions and directives

The Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission (Helsinki Commission, HELCOM), established in 1974, is an intergovernmental organization dedicated to protecting the marine environment of the Baltic Sea. To implement the Baltic Sea Action Plan (BSAP), HELCOM applies several marine ecosystem indicators with a scientific foundation. These include water quality indicators to assess the effect of eutrophication (e.g. water transparency, and nutrient, phytoplankton and zooplankton concentrations), pollution indicators (e.g. heavy metal, PCB and PAH concentrations) and biodiversity indicators (e.g. seal and harbor porpoise abundance and breeding success of birds). These indicators are aimed at assessing the status of the Baltic Sea according to the BSAP and the MSFD. The indicators must be scientifically sound, reflect relevant pressures, be quantitative, be regularly updated and be publicly available (HELCOM, 2013). By applying indicators of the marine ecosystem status in the Baltic Sea, the third holistic assessment has demonstrated measurable regional improvements in the focus areas of the BSAP and the MSFD, while also showing that the state of the Baltic Sea overall has not improved from 2016 to 2021 (HELCOM, 2023).

The OSPAR commission, which includes representatives from 15 countries and the European Union, is working collaboratively to protect and conserve the marine environment of the North-East Atlantic Ocean. To perform regular assessments of the ecosystem status of the North-East Atlantic, a set of common indicators were developed, ensuring consistency over time and space. The common indicators are based on the information from monitoring programs and are being continuously developed with a set of “candidate indicators”. Examples of indicators included in the OSPAR work are biodiversity (e.g. mammal, seal, bird and fish abundance), hazardous substances (e.g. heavy metal concentrations and PCB concentrations) and oil spills (OSPAR, <https://www.ospar.org/work-areas/cross-cutting-issues/ospar-common-indicators>).

The Barcelona Convention has been crucial for the development of ecosystem indicators in the Mediterranean Sea. It fosters regional cooperation between countries bordering the Mediterranean Sea and established a set of ecological objectives to guide management and assessment for the area under the framework of e.g. the MSFD in 2012. The indicators are part of the Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Program (IMAP) and include indicators like those used in the HELCOM Convention, such as biodiversity, pollution and habitats. The IMAP has thus led to improved monitoring and assessment of marine ecosystems, and enhanced science-based management (UNEP/MAP, 2017).

The WFD was established by the European Union in 2000 with the aim of protecting and enhancing the water quality of inland, transitional, and coastal waters (European Commission, 2000). To assess the status of the water, biological quality indicators, hydromorphological indicators and chemical quality indicators are used. The initial goal of the WFD was to obtain good ecological status of European water bodies by 2015. However, this goal was not feasible, and the deadline was first pushed to 2021 and secondly to 2027 (Water Framework Directive - European Commission).

The MSFD was adopted in 2008 by the EU, with the aim of sustaining healthy and resilient marine ecosystems and ensuring sustainable use of marine resources (European Commission, 2008). The main goal of the MSFD was initially to obtain good environmental status of marine waters by 2020. However, the targets were not reached, and Member States continue to work toward this goal. To guide the definition of good environmental status, the EU has defined eleven qualitative descriptors, each with associated indicators and targets. The descriptors cover the following topics: Biodiversity, non-indigenous species (NIS), commercial fish and shellfish, food webs, eutrophication, seafloor integrity, hydrographical conditions, contaminants, contaminants in seafood, marine litter and energy, including underwater noise.

3.2 Socio-economic and climatic indicators

3.2.1 Sectoral distribution of articles

We adopted an organizational approach stemming from the Eurostat dashboard of the Blue Economy Dashboard. The articles are categorized into thematic areas:

- Living resources: Fishing, aquaculture
- Non-living resources: Natural resources, artificial resources, heritage and cultural physical capital
- Tourism (coastal)
- Infrastructure: land effects on cities, coastal erosion, ports, transport, shipbuilding

An additional category includes articles providing some form of review of climate indicators. As shown in Figure 3-6 below, the number of sectors found in the analysis is relatively concentrated in a few key areas.

Figure 3-6: Distribution of sectors in the reviewed articles

Although most articles (33) refer to **infrastructure**, little to no research specifically deals with transport, shipbuilding, or ports. Most of the infrastructure-related articles delve into coastal erosion, sea-level rise and land changes induced by climate change, and more specifically its impacts on coastal dynamics and the marine environment, including alterations in chemical composition. The second biggest group falls under a heterogeneous category labeled **MIXED**. It includes studies dealing with indicators for mixed purposes, such as standards of living of local communities. Among the other

prominent categories are **Living Resources**, such as fishing and aquaculture, and **Tourism**. The articles referencing Living Resources regard not only fisheries but also protected areas and their vulnerability to climate change. Tourism is cited in various forms and often takes part in the MIXED group. **Non-Living Resources**, as classified by the EU (energy, minerals and cultural heritage), is the category less commonly cited, with cultural heritage being the main citation in this subgroup. Additionally, we found three articles of literature review.

Overall, we found that literature was not only focused on exploitation and risks of reduced yields but encompassed broader considerations such as biodiversity.

3.2.2 Distribution of climate indicator-related articles over time

We plotted in Figure 3-7 the distribution over the years for both relevant and irrelevant papers. This form allows us to discriminate when studies involving the creation of climate indicators become relevant. Although articles with the selected keywords date back to the 1990s, most of the research has emerged since the 2010s. This is probably related to the dissemination of databases elaborated with climate models and satellite information such as Copernicus in the EU and beyond. This suggests that the research objectives of the project are grounded in a recently developed field of literature, with potential for further expansion.

Figure 3-7: Trends in published papers

3.2.3 Coastal vulnerability

In synthesis, the articles collected in this literature review focused on the theme of Coastal vulnerability. Nearly all articles directly address coastal vulnerability, often relating it to climate change impacts like sea-level rise, storm surges, erosion, and extreme weather events. This vulnerability is assessed across diverse scales, ranging from local communities to entire nations and even global regions, with particular emphasis on the Mediterranean. This is a peculiar result, as neither the keywords nor the articles selection reflected a geographical reference, meaning that this issue is of particular interest in the Mediterranean region.

3.2.4 Relevance of socio-economic climate indicator-related literature over time

The relevance of the issue can be reflected by the number of citations. As shown in the previous plot, comparing the general stream of literature with that on socioeconomic climate indicators highlights their relative importance over time. Figure 3-8 below illustrates this synthesis.

Figure 3-8: Sum of citations per year

It is worth noting that while the theme has seen a significant increase in citations after 2010, the field of climate indicators has presented a fading trend over the past five years,

with the number of citations related to this theme decreasing year by year. However, the articles of our interest kept a relatively constant number of citations in the last ten years with some fluctuation. This potentially implies that there is interest among scholars and practitioners in the theme we are investigating. Since the former trend is a decreasing one and the latter is stable at worst, we can presume that this research subfield will become of most importance in the coming years.

3.2.5 Methodologies and research approaches

The studies employ a wide array of methods, including Index-based assessments. Various vulnerability indices (CVI, CCVI, PCVI, ECVI, DRI, etc.) are frequently used to quantify and compare vulnerability levels across different locations and factors. GIS and remote sensing are consistently used for spatial analysis, mapping vulnerability hotspots, and visualizing results. Hydrodynamic models, climate models (CMIP6), and other simulation tools are used to project future scenarios and estimate impacts. Some studies involve stakeholder engagement to incorporate local knowledge and perspectives in vulnerability assessments and risk management. Finally, some articles adopt an array of statistical analyses to generate and evaluate the relation between variables of coastal vulnerability. Correlation analyses, regression models, and other statistical techniques are employed to identify relationships between variables and assess the significance of trends. The goal of most studies is to inform decision-making for coastal management, risk reduction, and adaptation to climate change. Many articles propose specific adaptation strategies or policy recommendations.

3.2.6 Topic analysis

An analysis of the themes emerging in the collection of papers reveals that there is an overlap in the content. We used a Latent Dirichlet Algorithm to identify the main issues treated by the articles. Results showed two main themes, with significant overlap. We tried to implement the approach for more themes, but we found repetition in the content analysis, meaning that the algorithm had reached a point of saturation. This implies that in the research themes found in the collection are the most relevant ones. This overlap is observable in the word cloud plot of Figure 4, where “risk” and “index” are the main words

repeated in all cases. Other recurring terms refer to coastal climate risks, such as floods, hurricanes, and heat.

Figure 3-9: LDA topic modeling result

It is worth noting that both issues refer to coastal seas and are often connected to sea level rise, flooding, and heat. These themes are the ones that emerged in infrastructure-related research. This implies that these issues emerge with other research topics as well, indicating a saturation of research on these issues. These repetitions indicate that while peculiar aspects have been well addressed in the last years, other gaps are emerging. Several studies highlight the challenge of data scarcity, particularly for socioeconomic variables and long-term monitoring data in certain regions, especially in the Global South. This limits the accuracy and scope of some assessments.

3.3 Socio-economic data collection

We implemented a data collection process to support the integration of the socioeconomic dimension of coastal climate change impacts. The findings partially originated from the literature review, over which the group expert judgement was adopted to address the gaps that emerged from Scopus. A separate file outlines the key features of indicators, their application, data format, spatial and temporal coverage, and data accessibility. Data formats include NetCDF, CSV, XLSX, GRID, and TIFF. Accessibility

varies; some datasets are readily available via links provided (e.g., several Climate Data Store datasets), while others require access to research papers or publications. Some indicators show a "Transferred or Deprecated" status, indicating that the data is no longer directly available in the specified location.

The collection includes a variety of climate indicators relevant to various sectors, including tourism, health, and coastal management. Three indices (HCI, CIT, TCI) aim to quantify the impact of climate on tourism and are synthetic elaborations of climate data (Scott et al., 2016). While HCI and CIT share similar temporal and spatial resolutions (monthly, seasonal, yearly; ~12.5 km resolution across Europe), their availability differs; the newer versions are accessible, while older versions have been transferred or deprecated. TCI uses a different spatial resolution (NUTS2 regions within the EU) and is readily available. The UTCI and MRT indicators provide hourly data on thermal comfort at a relatively high spatial resolution (~27-28 km globally, excluding Antarctica) from 1940 to the present, available through the Climate Data Store.

MOIRAI aims to expand climate observatories' (such as Copernicus) informative capacity by synthesizing the relation between climate risk and socioeconomic performances of coastal anthropic environments, sectors and business models. Thus, various occupation indicators have been collected to identify regional-level performances with sector specifications. Regarding occupation, we selected NACE Occupation at the NUTS2 level. This indicator provides yearly data on occupations at the NUTS2 level within the EU from 2008-2023. We also collected the downscaled GDP and Population use 1km x 1km gridded data, covering varying periods. In contrast, downscaled per capita GDP offers a more detailed spatial breakdown but has different resolutions based on the country.

We also collected indicators that inform on immediate risk or damage to coastal anthropic activities, such as the probability of extreme events, chronic risks and others. These indicators, derived from CMIP6 projections, offer yearly, monthly, and daily data at varying resolutions (0.5° x 0.5° to 2.8125° x 2.8125°) from 1850 to 2300. The temporal coverage varies by model and product. The Coastal Risk Index provides yearly data with varying geographical resolutions depending on data availability. Projections of decreasing coastal flood protection offer data from 1850-2100 at varying resolutions,

focusing on the EU. Sea Level Rise data, encompassing reanalysis and projections, offers a high temporal resolution (down to 10-minute intervals) and varying spatial resolutions depending on proximity to the coast. "Chlorophyll in Europe's transitional, coastal and marine waters" provides monthly data from 1980-2021 at a spatial resolution dependent on distance from the coastline. Oxygen concentrations in Europe's coastal and marine waters lack detailed temporal and spatial coverage information.

3.4 Relationship between Life Cycle Analysis and indicators

Below is a list of indicators related to the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology that are linked to the indicators previously reported in each of the categories.

3.4.1 LCA indicator: Climate change

pH and Acidification

The increase in the concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere causes an increase in ocean acidification (Fabry et al., 2008). Bach et al. (2016) have developed a model that allows the increase in pH to be associated with GHG emissions. To do this, the authors mainly consider two key elements: the environmental fate of the pollutants and the chemical sensitivity of the ocean to these compounds.

Firstly, they calculate a "fate factor", which determines what proportion of each pollutant emitted dissolves in the ocean. This factor is obtained by multiplying three elements: the distribution (what fraction of the pollutant reaches the atmosphere), the conversion (what percentage of the pollutant is chemically transformed into CO₂), and finally the dissolution (what fraction of CO₂ dissolves in seawater).

Secondly, they use a "fate sensitivity factor", which measures how many hydrogen ions (H⁺) each substance releases once dissolved in the ocean, generating a decrease in pH. This factor considers the formation of bicarbonate and carbonate, which determine how many H⁺ ions are released for each gram of dissolved substance.

Scherer et al., (2022) defined characterization factors that allow the measurement of the potentially disappearing fraction (PDF) of species due to acidification. The methodology considers differences between highly calcifying species (corals, mollusks, echinoderms)

and poorly calcifying species (crustaceans, fish), as well as variations according to climate zone (tropics, temperate and polar regions).

From this perspective, pH variation results can be linked to GHG emissions, which can be incorporated into the life cycle analysis as part of the inventory.

Carbon sequestration in ocean ecosystems

Marine carbon sequestration is defined as a biogeochemical process by which CO₂ is fixed by living organisms, resulting in its storage and consequent reduction in the atmosphere (Garrard & Beaumont, 2014). One of these sequestration pathways is through the deposition of particulate organic matter on the seabed. The oceans are a major source of organic carbon storage, microorganisms such as phytoplankton, bacteria, archaea and protozoa represent more than 90% of the total marine biomass and are the main contributors to blue carbon (Zhang et al., 2017).

Vierros (2013) provides data on carbon storage capacities for different ecosystems, such as mangroves (3100-4400 tons of CO₂ eq/ha), marshes (362-2012 tons of CO₂ eq/ha) and seagrass beds (66-1478 tons of CO₂ eq/ha). Knowing the storage capacity of different marine ecosystems can be useful, CO₂ capture data can be translated into a flow of negative emissions within the framework of the LCA methodology.

Sea level rise

Sea level rise can cause coastal flooding. Relocating and adapting existing activities and buildings, as well as constructing infrastructure such as barriers, embankments, walls and dikes, are actions that reduce the impact associated with sea level rise (Andersson-Sköld et al., 2015). These measures require material and operating expenses that can be translated into flows that can be entered into the LCA inventory that can be translated into atmospheric emissions.

Sea level rise can also cause the deterioration or loss of terrestrial diversity and habitats. Dorber et al. (2019) have developed a series of characterization factors, allowing the estimation of the potential fraction of species lost (PDF/m²) due to land occupation. The

taxonomic groups of each region and the type of land use were considered in the calculation of these characterization factors.

3.4.2 LCA indicator: Marine ecotoxicity

Heavy metals and toxins (mercury, lead, PCBs)

Increased industrial activity has led to increased emissions of heavy metals, which can be discharged into marine environments causing damage to aquatic organisms and ecosystems (Nemr et al., 2012). Metals can be included in the inventory, for which it is necessary to know their concentration, volume of water or area affected.

Plastics and microplastics.

The presence of plastics in the oceans causes serious problems for the health of ecosystems (Cole et al., 2011). The LCA methodology includes characterization factors for three polymers—polypropylene (PP), low-density polyethylene (LDPE) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET)—so that it is possible to integrate these factors into the ReCiPe2016 method, within the marine ecotoxicity category (Schwarz et al. 2024).

The characterization factors were calculated at two levels: Midpoint, which quantifies the specific impact on the ecosystem in kg 1.4-DCB eq and Endpoint, which assesses the overall damage to the quality of the ecosystem in species/year. For the estimation, it is essential to have data on microplastic concentration and the affected areas or the plastic quantity by weight.

Høiberg et al. (2024) have established a series of endpoint characterization factors related to ecosystem quality due to the entanglement of fishing gear with macroplastics. To calculate this impact factor, data on the amount of plastic emitted by weight and the area where this plastic is released must be available. With this data, the final impact for the ecosystem quality category can be calculated as the fraction of species affected per kilogram of plastic emitted (PAF/kg).

3.4.3 LCA indicator: Marine eutrophication

Nutrient level

Eutrophication is an environmental problem caused by an excess of nutrients, especially nitrogen and phosphorus (Henderson et al., 2021). The LCA provides a standardized quantitative framework that allows the assessment of the eutrophication potential (kg N_{eq} and kg P_{eq}). To calculate this impact, it is necessary to know the amount of nitrogen and phosphorus emitted and the geographical location.

Diversity and abundance of plankton, primary production (chlorophyll-a)

Primary producers such as plankton play a fundamental role in the coastal marine ecosystems, sustaining the rest of the trophic levels. However, excessive nutrient input can lead to overaccumulation (Garmendia et al., 2010). Chlorophyll concentration is one of the common measures of phytoplankton biomass and is commonly used as an indirect indicator of phytoplankton biomass.

3.4.4 LCA indicator: Ecosystem quality

Fishing and capture per unit of effort

The overfishing of large vertebrates and shellfish, the loss of species and of biomass affects the quality of ecosystems. The ecological extinction of trophic levels in marine ecosystems causes an increase in vulnerability to other types of disturbance (Jackson et al., 2001). Hélias et al. (2023) propose a new way of including fishing in LCA through the final category of ecosystem quality. This integration is achieved through new characterization factors that allow the evaluation of fishing on biodiversity in terms compatible with standard LCA methodologies such as ReCiPe. The result is expressed in species·Year/kg of fish.

To calculate this impact, data on fish stocks, catches, current stock biomass, growth rates and geographical distribution are required. In addition to this, inventory data on the materials and fuels used for fishing are also necessary.

Discards

Vázquez-Rowe et al. (2012) highlight the importance of including discards in the LCA of different fishing gears. Discards, defined as the part of the catch that is thrown back into the sea dead or alive, generate significant ecological impacts, such as the alteration of biodiversity and the modification of trophic interactions. Including these factors in the LCA allows for a more comprehensive assessment of the sustainability of fisheries and improves decision-making in their management. To calculate this new impact, it is necessary to know the catches by species, trophic level by species, and the discard and landing rates.

Invasive species

Invasive species are one of the elements responsible for the loss of biodiversity, this introduction being mainly due to long-distance maritime transport routes. Invasive species can be transported in ballast water, attached to ship hulls, aquaculture and the operation and construction of canals (Bax et al., 2003).

Myklebust, M. N. (2019) proposes a model to determine the impact of invasive species using characterization factors within LCA for the ecosystem quality category. This model considers the amount of m³ of ballast water transported and the region in which it is released. To calculate these factors, it is necessary to know the number of invasive species in a region, the number of native species, the number of affected native species, the volume of ballast water and the frequency of discharge in a region. Once the characterization factors for each region have been determined, it is necessary to enter the volume of ballast water in the inventory.

Noise

Middel and Verones (2017) introduce the impact of marine noise pollution on cetaceans by integrating characterization factors related to the ecosystem quality category. To quantify this impact, it is necessary to know data such as the source and level of noise, its propagation in the water, the species affected, areas of avoidance by the affected species, and the time and duration of exposure.

3.4.5 LCA indicator: Land use or “Seabed use”

Biodiversity and species richness, coastal development and habitat destruction, mangroves and seagrass beds

Seagrass meadows represent one of the most productive ecosystems on Earth, providing high-value ecosystem services such as fisheries provisioning, nutrient cycling and carbon sequestration (Waycott et al., 2009). Mangroves play an important role in coastal protection, acting as natural barriers against storms, hurricanes and coastal erosion. They provide defense against flooding and are home to a wide variety of species. Mangroves have been affected by human activities, decreasing in area and losing quality due to different pressures, such as climate change, eutrophication and land use change (He et al., 2025). Woods and Verones (2018) address the problem of the destruction of marine habitat due to human activities such as trawling, marine mining and construction on the seabed, which affect the biodiversity and integrity of benthic ecosystems.

The proposed method for including the destruction of marine habitat in the LCA uses an impact characterization model based on two approaches: the single impact perspective, which assesses the damage of a disturbance event considering the spatial and temporal scale, the initial response of the ecosystem and the time for ecological recovery, and the repeated impact perspective, which analyzes the cumulative effects when the frequency of disturbances (such as trawling) exceeds the time required for recovery. Transformation and occupation characterization factors (CFs) have been developed in terms of relative species loss (PDF.year/m²).

To include this impact in the LCA it is necessary to know data on the affected area, type of ecosystem, intensity of the disturbance, frequency of disturbance (cyclical impacts), ecological recovery times of the different ecosystems and variation in the distribution of species after the impact.

3.4.6 LCA indicator: Human health

Heavy metals and toxins (mercury, lead, PCBs), oil spills and chemical pollutants

These pollutants are mainly emitted by oil spills, boat traffic as well as wastewater discharges. To introduce these compounds into the LCA, it is necessary to identify the emission source and location, its composition and the emission flows.

3.4.7 New LCA indicator: Depletion of biotic resources

If we know the intensity of fishing and the state of the stocks, we can identify the environmental impacts related to the depletion of natural resources. Langlois et al. (2014) described a method for integrating these values into the LCA. This method considers two levels of impact: at the species level, evaluating the decline of a specific stock due to fishing, and at the ecosystem level, measuring the total biomass availability in the oceans. To do this, the relationship between the catch of a species and its maximum sustainable yield (MSY) is calculated, as well as the amount of net primary production (NPP) removed from the ecosystem, adjusted for the productivity of the fishing area.

The usefulness of this method lies in its ability to provide a quantitative assessment of the impact of fishing on biotic resources, allowing for a more accurate comparison between different species and regions. By including scarcity factors and differentiating between impacts at the species and ecosystem level, this approach improves the accuracy of LCA in the fishing sector.

4. Discussion

4.1 Current use of indicators

While many studies acknowledge the interconnectedness of social and ecological systems, fully integrating both aspects into comprehensive vulnerability assessments remains a significant challenge. More research is needed to quantify the complex interactions between social vulnerability and ecosystem services. Various articles have suggested defining climate risk indicators according to compounding events and factors. The risk of multiple hazards occurring concurrently (compound events) is increasingly recognized, but there is still limited research explicitly addressing this issue, particularly in the context of vulnerability assessment and adaptation planning (Ameca et al., 2024). Another gap in the literature refers to equity and justice implications of climate change affecting coastal communities. While some studies touch upon the issue, a more systematic exploration of how climate-related impacts disproportionately affect vulnerable populations is needed. This includes understanding the distribution of risks and benefits associated with adaptation measures. Furthermore, while exposure connected to economic inequality and relative poverty has been studied in detail in growing economies, it has received less attention in developed areas and in the Mediterranean (Ehsan et al., 2022; Rouleau et al., 2022).

Finally, there are two more gaps that entail the reference of data and the reproducibility of results, which the project MOIRAI is capable of filling. Many vulnerability assessments are snapshot studies rather than continuous monitoring efforts. More long-term monitoring and validation of index-based approaches and model projections are crucial to verify their accuracy and refine assessment methods. Secondly, while indices are applied across various scales, the transferability of methodologies and findings between different geographical regions and contexts requires further investigation.

With respect to the sectors provided by the Blue Economy Dashboard, we find that there is a need for further research regarding indicators of social resilience. These indicators might be tied to cultural assets, inequality in regions, and the exposure to extreme events and sea-level rise. Biodiversity loss has been widely studied in literature and should be

connected to the welfare of local communities as well, with consistent and long-term outlooks. For instance, it might be possible to infer shifts in the diets of coastal populations due to losses in fisheries and carrying capacity. Although infrastructure-related studies are the most common, studies on energy supply remain relatively limited. Yet, climate change will affect current and therefore impact the viability of alternative energy sources such as wave and tidal. Additionally, offshore wind turbines are particularly vulnerable to extreme events, whose changes in frequency could threaten their durability and long-term functionality, thereby accelerating their depreciation.

4.2 Numerical models as tools for marine ecosystem indicators

Assessing ecosystem health using biogeochemical-, ecosystem-, and ocean regional-modeling-data opens new opportunities in terms of being able to provide large amounts of information in space and time, without the logistical challenges of obtaining ship- or buoy-based observations from the field. However, utilizing models to provide indicators also comes with a number of challenges. Firstly, while the large-scale ocean currents are often well-captured by numerical models, small scale processes, such as turbulent flow, are usually not fully resolved. This will impact the modeled description of e.g. vertical nutrient mixing and transport of early life stages of larvae. Achieving a realistic numerical representation of ecosystems requires not just a realistic representation of each component, but also consideration of the dynamic interactions between physical, biogeochemical, and biological processes across diverse temporal and spatial scales. This necessitates a comprehensive understanding of how ecosystems respond to changing abiotic conditions, an area that remains largely uncertain due to the limited knowledge of the physiological responses of many species to environmental changes. However, current physical ocean models effectively capture abiotic dynamics of the pelagic system and changes therein, making them valuable for forecasting future abiotic scenarios and worth considering as indicators of change (Jacox et al., 2023).

While numerical simulation of physical ocean processes relies on physical laws, biological processes in numerical models are based on parameterizations, which

simplify complex natural processes into manageable mathematical representations. This simplification is necessary as many biological processes occur on a scale too small or complex to be adequately described by numerical models. Examples of parameterizations are aggregation of species into functional groups, or fluxes of elements between different compartments in the model, e.g. between dissolved nutrients and organic matter. The question is whether all variables in biogeochemical models are sufficiently constrained to be used for indicators (Ciavatta et al., 2025). While the lower trophic levels of ecosystems, often denoted biogeochemical models, are more well-constrained, the higher trophic levels, such as fish and cetaceans are more challenging to adequately describe. Often the higher trophic levels are treated in food-web models, in which potential impacts of multiple stressors and management strategies on the ecosystem can be tested. Consequently, holistic food-web model studies focusing on impacts of climate change on ecosystem structure and function remain relatively rare. Further, while simpler indicators, such as nutrient and chlorophyll concentrations, are possible to describe in a range of models, more complicated indicators, such as biodiversity and habitats, are more challenging, illustrating how the use of physical and biological ocean models to derive ecosystem health indices still presents both fundamental and technical challenges (e.g., Horn et al., 2021).

However, while developing ecosystem-based indicators is challenging, the need for e.g. management of marine resources and climate change mitigation makes it necessary to bridge the gap between marine ecosystem and socio-economic indicators. Effective integration of marine biology with socio-economic research requires collaboration between scientists of differing disciplines, something that can be challenging due to differences in terminologies, methods and research goals. Further, translating complex ecosystem interactions into simple and relevant socio-economic questions and developing these into actionable policies is a major challenge, involving navigating the political regulatory landscape.

4.3 MOIRAI models and indicator work

4.3.1 The Arctic

The Iceland-Scotland Ridge in the European Arctic region is a critical transition zone of hydrodynamic and environmental characteristics between the North Atlantic and the Arctic Ocean. It plays a key role in forming deep waters and the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC), directly influencing the ecosystem, productivity and fisheries (Pampoulie et al., 2024). In the MOIRAI project, the global sea ice model FESOM2 will be coupled to the regional model FESOM-C, which in turn is coupled to the biogeochemical model REcoM3 to simulate oceanic and biogeochemical processes in this area, which will provide information on physical and biogeochemical indices. Particular attention in this part of the project will be paid to climate oceanographic indices, including heat transport, sea surface temperature (SST) and AMOC variability, as these factors are responsible for physical and biological processes in the region (de Marez et al., 2024). Other equally essential indices - nutrient, chlorophyll, oxygen concentrations and net primary productivity - are also particularly interesting within the project.

Sea ice plays a major role for the local communities in the Arctic. Retreating sea ice has both positive and negative effects and they will require adaptation. A reduced sea ice cover will allow new ship routes, reduce the need for ice strengthening of vessels etc. On the other hand, sea ice and especially landfast sea ice is important for travel, hunting and fishing. With the reduced ice cover waves will propagate further into areas that are not usually affected, and the combined effect will potentially lead to increased erosion and potential for larger storm surges. Storm surges, in particular, will be a key focus within MOIRAI. As a demonstration case, Disko Bay will be simulated with a high resolution that resolves the complex topography within the fjord and therefore allows for better sea ice and water level estimates.

4.3.2 The North Sea

The North Sea ecosystem is a highly productive and diverse marine environment undergoing significant changes due to human activities, including the rapid expansion of offshore wind farms. Human activities are having a range of effects on the ecosystem, and monitoring the health of the environment is crucial to ensure sustainable growth. Various ecosystem indices are used to assess and track these changes, focusing on the physical, biological, and ecological components of the system through e.g. the work in the OSPAR Commission (www.ospar.org). Lower trophic multi-use aquaculture provides ecosystem services by removing nutrients and carbon from the water column, while providing seafood through mussel and kelp harvesting (Maar et al., 2023). In the framework of the MOIRAI project, lower trophic aquaculture farms will be incorporated into the FlexSem regional North Sea model (Larsen et al., 2020). For the indicator development this model setup can provide oceanographic variables, such as temperature and salinity, it can provide biogeochemical indicators of e.g. eutrophication, such as nutrient, oxygen and chlorophyll concentrations, and it can provide information on mussel size, mussel growth, as well as harvested mussel and kelp biomass from the aquaculture model.

4.3.3 Mediterranean Sea

In the Western Mediterranean, the project will support Mediterranean fishery management by assessing the model predictability of focus commercial fish species (e.g., anchovy, sardine, European hake, etc.), and by simulating the response of these species to climate change. Model predictability will be assessed at different spatial scales.

In Greek waters, the impact of climate change on mussel aquaculture will be assessed. Variables available for indicator work are e.g. temperature, pH, nutrient concentration and chlorophyll concentration, as well as information from the aquaculture, such as growth rate and biomass of the farmed mussels, and information on fish stocks.

5. Concluding remarks

The analysis of marine ecosystem indicators showed that especially benthic biodiversity and eutrophication indicators have been widely used. Development of standardized indices has been pushed forward, for benthic ecosystem quality, biodiversity and resilience, aligning with the MSFD target of the EU. In recent years, an effort towards holistic assessments of marine ecosystem status has taken place, leading to comprehensive tools for ecosystem assessment such as the NEAT. However, other topics such as invasive species, habitat changes and the biodiversity and resilience of fish population receive comparably less attention, likely due to both the complexity of data collection and analysis. The MOIRAI project will be able to work on reducing this gap by working on indicators for aquaculture and commercial fish species in the North Sea and the Mediterranean, respectively.

The analysis of socio-economic indicators showed gaps and inconsistencies that the MOIRAI project can address. Research on evaluating climate impacts on infrastructure, in particular coastal erosion and sea level rise, is well developed, but gaps on transport or renewable energy supply were revealed. Other fields of study, such as living resources and tourism, are less prevalent, while research on non-living resources is quasi-absent. The literature review also demonstrated a strong focus on developing economies, while research on developed regions, including the Mediterranean, that are the focus of the MOIRAI project, is lacking.

Despite progress in the development of climate synthetic indicators, the integration of socio-economic data with ecological and physical factors lacks standardization, which hinders long-term monitoring and actionability. By establishing standardized interdisciplinary climate synthetic indicators, MOIRAI will support better-informed decision making and enhance coastal resilience and sustainable management.

6. References

- Alejandre, E. M., Van Bodegom, P. M., & Guinée, J. B. (2019). Towards an optimal coverage of ecosystem services in LCA. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, *231*, 714–722. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.05.284>
- Ameca, E. I., Nie, Y., Wu, R., Mittermeier, R. A., Foden, W., & Wei, F. (2024). Identifying protected areas in biodiversity hotspots at risk from climate and human-induced compound events for conserving threatened species. *Science of The Total Environment*, *938*, 173192. [10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.173192](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.173192)
- Andersson-Sköld, Y., Thorsson, S., Rayner, D., Lindberg, F., Janhäll, S., Jonsson, A., Moback, U., Bergman, R., & Granberg, M. (2015). An integrated method for assessing climate-related risks and adaptation alternatives in urban areas. *Climate Risk Management*, *7*, 31–50. [10.1016/j.crm.2015.01.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crm.2015.01.003)
- Baas, J., Schotten, M., Plume, A., Côté, G., & Karimi, R. (2020). Scopus as a curated, high-quality bibliometric data source for academic research in quantitative science studies. *Quantitative science studies*, *1*(1), 377-386, [10.1162/qss_a_00019](https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00019)
- Bach, V., Möller, F., Finogenova, N., Emarā, Y., & Finkbeiner, M. (2016). Characterization model to assess ocean acidification within life cycle assessment. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, *21*(10), 1463–1472. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1121-x>
- Bax, N., Williamson, A., Agüero, M., Gonzalez, E., & Geeves, W. (2003). Marine invasive alien species: a threat to global biodiversity. *Marine Policy*, *27*(4), 313–323. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0308-597x\(03\)00041-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0308-597x(03)00041-1)
- Boldt, J. L., Hazen, E. L., Hunsicker, M. E., Fu, C., Perry, R. I., & Shan, X. (2021). Quantifying ecosystem responses to environmental and human pressures in the marine ecosystem off the west coast of Vancouver Island. *Ecological Indicators*, *132*, 108232, [10.1016/j.ecolind.2021.108232](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2021.108232).

- Borja, A., Franco, J., & Pérez, V. (2000). A marine biotic index to establish the ecological quality of soft-bottom benthos within European estuarine and coastal environments. *Marine pollution bulletin*, 40(12), 1100-1114, 10.1016/S0025-326X(00)00061-8.
- Borja, Á., Dauer, D. M., & Grémare, A. (2012). The importance of setting targets and reference conditions in assessing marine ecosystem quality. *Ecological Indicators*, 12(1), 1-7, 10.1016/j.ecolind.2011.06.018.
- Borja, A., Elliott, M., Andersen, J. H., Berg, T., Carstensen, J., Halpern, B. S., Heiskanen, A.-S., Korpinen, S., Lowndes, J., Martin, G. & Rodriguez-Ezpeleta, N. (2016). Overview of integrative assessment of marine systems: the ecosystem approach in practice. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 3, 20, 10.3389/fmars.2016.00020.
- Bryndum-Buchholz, A., Eddy, T. D., & Fisher, J. A. (2025). Assessing indirect biodiversity conservation benefits of fisheries closures in the Gulf of St. Lawrence, Canada. *PLoS one*, 20(1), e0316754, 10.1371/journal.pone.0316754.
- Carlson, R. E. (1977). A trophic state index for lakes 1. *Limnology and oceanography*, 22(2), 361-369, 10.4319/lo.1977.22.2.0361.
- Ciavatta, S., Lazzari, P., Álvarez, E., Bertino, L., Bolding, K., Bruggeman, J., Capet, A., Cossarini, G., Daryabor, F., Nerger, L., Popov, M., Skakala, J., Spada, S., Teruzzi, A., Wakamatsu, T., Yumruktepec, V. C. & Brasseur, P. (2025). Control of simulated ocean ecosystem indicators by biogeochemical observations. *Progress in Oceanography*, 231, 103384, 10.1016/j.pocean.2024.103384.
- Cole, M., Lindeque, P., Halsband, C., & Galloway, T. S. (2011). Microplastics as contaminants in the marine environment: A review. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 62(12), 2588–2597. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2011.09.025>
- Cruz-Ramírez, C. J., Chávez, V., Silva, R., Muñoz-Perez, J. J., & Rivera-Arriaga, E. (2024). Coastal Management: A Review of Key Elements for Vulnerability Assessment. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 12(3), 386. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse12030386>

- Dagnino, A., Allen, J. I., Moore, M. N., Broeg, K., Canesi, L., & Viarengo, A. (2007). Development of an expert system for the integration of biomarker responses in mussels into an animal health index. *Biomarkers*, 12(2), 155-172, 10.1080/13547500601037171.
- Dale, V. H., & Beyeler, S. C. (2001). Challenges in the development and use of ecological indicators. *Ecological indicators*, 1(1), 3-10, 10.1016/S1470-160X(01)00003-6.
- Dauvin, J. C., & Ruellet, T. (2009). The estuarine quality paradox: is it possible to define an ecological quality status for specific modified and naturally stressed estuarine ecosystems?. *Marine pollution bulletin*, 59(1-3), 38-47, 10.1016/j.marpolbul.2008.11.008.
- De Luca Peña, L. V., Dewulf, J., Staes, J., Moulart, I., Vandamme, S., Heymans, J. J., & Taelman, S. E. (2024). Assessing the sustainability of Blue Economy activities using an ecosystem and life cycle-based approach: Possibilities, challenges and implications for an informed policy making. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 257, 107360. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2024.107360>
- De Souza, D. M., Lopes, G. R., Hansson, J., & Hansen, K. (2018). Ecosystem services in life cycle assessment: A synthesis of knowledge and recommendations for biofuels. *Ecosystem Services*, 30, 200–210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2018.02.014>
- Dorber, M., Kuipers, K., & Verones, F. (2019). Global characterization factors for terrestrial biodiversity impacts of future land inundation in Life Cycle Assessment. *The Science of the Total Environment*, 712, 134582. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.134582>
- Ehsan, S., Ara Begum, R., & Nizam Abdul Maulud, K. (2022). Household external vulnerability due to climate change in Selangor coast of Malaysia. *Climate Risk Management*, 35, 100408. 10.1016/j.crm.2022.100408
- European Commission, 2000. Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for community action in the field of water policy: 1–72. Brussels: EC.

- European Commission, 2008. Directive 2008/56/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008, establishing a framework for community action in the field of marine environmental policy (Marine Strategy Framework Directive).
- Fabry, V. J., Seibel, B. A., Feely, R. A., & Orr, J. C. (2008). Impacts of ocean acidification on marine fauna and ecosystem processes. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 65(3), 414–432. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsn048>
- Filho, L. M., P. Roebeling, S. Villasante and M. I. Bastos (2022). "Ecosystem services values and changes across the Atlantic coastal zone: Considerations and implications." *Marine Policy* 145: 105265.
- Garmendia, M., Revilla, M., Bald, J., Franco, J., Laza-Martínez, A., Orive, E., Seoane, S., Valencia, V., & Borja, Á. (2010). Phytoplankton communities and biomass size structure (fractionated chlorophyll "a"), along trophic gradients of the Basque coast (northern Spain). *Biogeochemistry*, 106(2), 243–263. [10.1007/s10533-010-9445-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-010-9445-2)
- Garrard, S. L., & Beaumont, N. J. (2014). The effect of ocean acidification on carbon storage and sequestration in seagrass beds; a global and UK context. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 86(1–2), 138–146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2014.07.032>
- Giovanardi, F., & Vollenweider, R. A. (2004). Trophic conditions of marine coastal waters: experience in applying the Trophic Index TRIX to two areas of the Adriatic and Tyrrhenian seas. *Journal of Limnology*, 63(2), 199-218, [10.4081/jlimnol.2004.199](https://doi.org/10.4081/jlimnol.2004.199).
- Grégoire, M., Garçon, V., Garcia, H., Breitburg, D., Isensee, K., Oschlies, A., Telszewski, M., Barth, A., Bittig, H., Carstensen, J., Carval, T., Chai, F., Chavez, D., Conley, D., Coppola, L., Crowe, S., Currie, K., Dai, M., Deflandre, B., Dewitte, B., Diaz, R., Garcia-Robledo, E., Gilbert, D., Giorgetti, A., Glud, R., Gutierrez, D., Hosoda, S., Ishii, M., Jacinto, G., Langdon, C., Lauvset, S., Levin, L., Limburg, K., Mehrtens, H., Montes, I., Naqvi, W., Paulmier, A., Pfeil, B., Pitcher, G., Pouliquen, S., Rabalais, N., Rabouille, C., Recape, V., Roman, M., Rose, K., Rudnick, D., Rummer, J., Schmechtig, C., Schmidtko, S., Seibel, B., Slomp, C., Sumalia, R., Tanhua, T., Thierry, V., Uchida, H., Wanninkhof, R., Yasuhara (2021). A global ocean oxygen database and atlas for assessing and predicting

- deoxygenation and ocean health in the open and coastal ocean. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8, 724913, 10.3389/fmars.2021.724913.
- Haddaway, N. R., Macura, B., Whaley, P., & Pullin, A. S. (2018). ROSES RepOrting standards for Systematic Evidence Syntheses: pro forma, flow-diagram and descriptive summary of the plan and conduct of environmental systematic reviews and systematic maps. *Environmental Evidence*, 7, 1-8, 10.1186/s13750-018-0121-7.
- Hauschild, M. Z., Rosenbaum, R. K., & Olsen, S. I. (2018). *Life cycle assessment* (Vol. 2018). Springer International Publishing, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-56475-3>.
- He, Q., Li, Z., Daleo, P. *et al.* Coastal wetland resilience through local, regional and global conservation. *Nat. Rev. Biodivers.* 1, 50–67 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44358-024-00004-x>
- HELCOM. (2013). HELCOM core indicators: Final report of the HELCOM CORESET project. *Baltic Sea Environment Proceedings No. 136*.
- HELCOM. (2023). State of the Baltic Sea. Third HELCOM holistic assessment 2016–2021. *Baltic Sea Enviro Proc*, 194, 69.
- Hélias, A., Stanford-Clark, C., & Bach, V. (2023). A new impact pathway towards ecosystem quality in life cycle assessment: Characterization factors for fisheries. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 28(4), 367–379. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-023-02136-2>
- Henderson, A. D., Niblick, B., Golden, H. E., & Bare, J. C. (2021). Modeling spatially resolved characterization factors for eutrophication potential in life cycle assessment. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 26(9), 1832–1846. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-021-01956-4>
- Horn, S., Meunier, C. L., Fofonova, V., Wiltshire, K. H., Sarker, S., Pogoda, B., & Asmus, H. (2021). Toward improved model capacities for assessment of climate impacts on coastal benthic-pelagic food webs and ecosystem services. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8, 567266, 10.3389/fmars.2021.567266.

- Høiberg, M. A., Stadler, K., & Verones, F. (2024). Disentangling marine plastic impacts in Life Cycle Assessment: Spatially explicit Characterization Factors for ecosystem quality. *The Science of the Total Environment*, 949, 175019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.175019>
- International Organization for Standardization. (2006). ISO 14040: Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework. ISO.
- International Organization for Standardization. (2006). ISO 14044: Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines. ISO.
- IPBES (2024). Summary for Policymakers of the Thematic Assessment Report on the Underlying Causes of Biodiversity Loss and the Determinants of Transformative Change and Options for Achieving the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. O'Brien, K., Garibaldi, L., Agrawal, A., Bennett, E., Biggs, O., Calderón Contreras, R., Carr, E., Frantzeskaki, N., Gosnell, H., Gurung, J., Lambertucci, S., Leventon, J., Liao, C., Reyes García, V., Shannon, L., Villasante, S., Wickson, F., Zinngrebe, Y., and Perianin, L. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382230>
- Jacox, M. G., Buil, M. P., Brodie, S., Alexander, M. A., Amaya, D. J., Bograd, S. J., ... & Tommasi, D. (2023). Downscaled seasonal forecasts for the California Current System: Skill assessment and prospects for living marine resource applications. *PLOS Climate*, 2(10), e0000245.
- Jackson, J. B. C., Kirby, M. X., Berger, W. H., Bjorndal, K. A., Botsford, L. W., Bourque, B. J., Bradbury, R. H., Cooke, R., Erlandson, J., Estes, J. A., Hughes, T. P., Kidwell, S., Lange, C. B., Lenihan, H. S., Pandolfi, J. M., Peterson, C. H., Steneck, R. S., Tegner, M. J., & Warner, R. R. (2001). Historical overfishing and the recent collapse of coastal ecosystems. *Science*, 293(5530), 629–637. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1059199>
- Kadin, M., Blenckner, T., Casini, M., Gårdmark, A., Torres, M. A., & Otto, S. A. (2019). Trophic interactions, management trade-offs and climate change: The need for adaptive

- thresholds to operationalize ecosystem indicators. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 6, 249, 10.3389/fmars.2019.00249.
- Langlois, J., Fréon, P., Steyer, J., Delgenès, J., & Hélias, A. (2014). Sea-use impact category in life cycle assessment: state of the art and perspectives. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 19(5), 994–1006. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-014-0700-y>
- Langlois, J., Fréon, P., Delgenes, J., Steyer, J., & Hélias, A. (2014). New methods for impact assessment of biotic-resource depletion in life cycle assessment of fisheries: theory and application. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 73, 63–71. 10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.01.087
- Larsen, J., Mohn, C., Pastor, A., & Maar, M. (2020). A versatile marine modelling tool applied to arctic, temperate and tropical waters. *PLoS One*, 15(4), e0231193, 10.1371/journal.pone.0231193.
- Laureate, C. D. P., Buntine, W., & Linger, H. (2023). A systematic review of the use of topic models for short text social media analysis. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 56(12), 14223–14255. 10.1007/s10462-023-10471-x
- Link, J. S., Yemane, D., Shannon, L. J., Coll, M., Shin, Y. J., Hill, L., & Borges, M. D. F. (2010). Relating marine ecosystem indicators to fishing and environmental drivers: an elucidation of contrasting responses. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 67(4), 787–795, 10.1093/icesjms/fsp258.
- Lopes, R., & Videira, N. (2013). Valuing marine and coastal ecosystem services: An integrated participatory framework. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 84, 153–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2013.08.001>
- Maar, M., Holbach, A., Boderskov, T., Thomsen, M., Buck, B. H., Kotta, J., & Bruhn, A. (2023). Multi-use of offshore wind farms with low-trophic aquaculture can help achieve global sustainability goals. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 4(1), 447, 10.1038/s43247-023-01116-6.

- de Marez, C., Ruiz-Angulo, A., & Le Corre, M. (2024). Structure of the bottom boundary current south of Iceland and spreading of deep waters by submesoscale processes. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 51(5), e2023GL107508, 10.1029/2023GL107508
- Margalef, R. (1973). Information theory in ecology.
- Middel, H., & Verones, F. (2017). Making Marine Noise Pollution Impacts Heard: The Case of Cetaceans in the North Sea within Life Cycle Impact Assessment. *Sustainability*, 9(7), 1138. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9071138>
- Myklebust, M. N. (2019). Developing a characterization factor and effect factor model for impacts of marine invasive species-Within the context of Life Cycle Impact Assessment (Master's thesis, NTNU).
- Nemr, A. E., Khaled, A., Moneer, A. A., & Sikaily, A. E. (2012). Risk probability due to heavy metals in bivalve from Egyptian Mediterranean coast. *The Egyptian Journal of Aquatic Research*, 38(2), 67–75. 10.1016/j.ejar.2012.11.001
- Pampoulie, C., Brix, S., & Randhawa, H. S. (2024). The Greenland–Scotland Ridge in a Changing Ocean: Time to Act?. *Marine Ecology*, e12830, 10.1111/maec.12830.
- Pielou, E. C. (1966). The measurement of diversity in different types of biological collections. *Journal of theoretical biology*, 13, 131-144, 10.1016/0022-5193(66)90013-0.
- Pinna, M., Zangaro, F., Saccomanno, B., Scalone, C., Bozzeda, F., Fanini, L., & Specchia, V. (2023). An overview of ecological indicators of fish to evaluate the anthropogenic pressures in aquatic ecosystems: from traditional to innovative DNA-based approaches. *Water*, 15(5), 949, 10.3390/w15050949.
- Pitois, S., & Yebra, L. (2022). Contribution of marine zooplankton time series to the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 79(3), 722-726, 10.1093/icesjms/fsac048.
- Rani, G., Kaur, J., Kumar, A., & Yogalakshmi, K. N. (2019). Ecosystem health and dynamics: An indicator of global climate change. In *Contemporary environmental issues and*

- challenges in era of climate change* (pp. 1-32). Singapore: Springer Singapore, 10.1007/978-981-32-9595-7_1.
- Rosenbaum, R.K. et al. (2018). Life Cycle Impact Assessment. In: Hauschild, M., Rosenbaum, R., Olsen, S. (eds) *Life Cycle Assessment*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-56475-3_10
- Rosenberg, R., Blomqvist, M., Nilsson, H. C., Cederwall, H., & Dimming, A. (2004). Marine quality assessment by use of benthic species-abundance distributions: a proposed new protocol within the European Union Water Framework Directive. *Marine pollution bulletin*, 49(9-10), 728-739, 1 0.1016/j.marpolbul.2004.05.013.
- Rouleau, T., Stuart, J., Call, M., Yozell, S., Yoshioka, N., Maekawa, M., & Fiertz, N. (2022). The climate and ocean risk vulnerability index: Measuring coastal city resilience to inform action. *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities*, 4. 10.3389/frsc.2022.884212
- Scherer, L., Gürdal, İ., & Van Bodegom, P. M. (2022). Characterization factors for ocean acidification impacts on marine biodiversity. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 26(6), 2069–2079. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13274>
- Schwarz, A., Herlaar, S., Cohen, Q., Quik, J., Golkaram, M., Urbanus, J., Van Emmerik, T., & Huijbregts, M. (2024). Microplastic aquatic impacts included in Life Cycle Assessment. *Resources Conservation and Recycling*, 209, 107787. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2024.107787>
- Scott, D., Ruttly, M., Amelung, B., & Tang, M. (2016). An inter-comparison of the Holiday Climate Index (HCI) and the Tourism Climate Index (TCI) in Europe. *Atmosphere*, 7(6), 23–28. 10.3390/atmos7060080
- Shin, Y. J., Houle, J. E., Akoglu, E., Blanchard, J. L., Bundy, A., Coll, M., Demarcq, H., Fu, C., Fulton, E., Heymans, J., Salihoglu, B., Shannon, L., Sporcic, M. & Velez, L. (2018). The specificity of marine ecological indicators to fishing in the face of environmental change: a multi-model evaluation. *Ecological Indicators*, 89, 317-326.

- Simboura, N., & Zenetos, A. (2002). Benthic indicators to use in ecological quality classification of Mediterranean soft bottom marine ecosystems, including a new biotic index. *Mediterranean Marine Science*, 3(2), 77-111, 10.12681/mms.249.
- Smith, C. J., Papadopoulou, K. N., Barnard, S., Mazik, K., Elliott, M., Patrício, J., Solaun, O., Little, S., Bhatia, N. & Borja, A. (2016). Managing the marine environment, conceptual models and assessment considerations for the European marine strategy framework directive. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 3, 144, 10.3389/fmars.2016.00144.
- Teixeira, H., Berg, T., Uusitalo, L., Fürhaupter, K., Heiskanen, A. S., Mazik, K., Lynam, C., Neville, S., Rodriguez, J., Papadopoulou, N., Moncheva, S., Churilova, T., Kryvenko, O., Krause-Jensen, D., Zaiko, A., Verissimo, H., Pantazi, M., Carvalho, S., Patricio, J., Uyarra, M. & Borja, À. (2016). A catalogue of marine biodiversity indicators. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 3, 207, 10.3389/fmars.2016.00207.
- Trifonova, N., Scott, B., De Dominicis, M., & Wolf, J. (2022). Use of our future seas: relevance of spatial and temporal scale for physical and biological indicators. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8, 769680, 10.1111/ecog.06925.
- Troast, B., Paperno, R., & Cook, G. S. (2020). Multidecadal shifts in fish community diversity across a dynamic biogeographic transition zone. *Diversity and Distributions*, 26(1), 93-107, 10.1111/ddi.13000.
- Turnhout, E., Hisschemöller, M., & Eijsackers, H. (2007). Ecological indicators: between the two fires of science and policy. *Ecological indicators*, 7(2), 215-228, 10.1016/j.ecolind.2005.12.003.
- UNEP/MAP. (2017). Mediterranean Quality status report. United Nations Environment/Mediterranean Action Plan Barcelona Convention Secretariat.
- Uusitalo, L., Blanchet, H., Andersen, J. H., Beauchard, O., Berg, T., Bianchelli, S., Cantafaro, A., Carstensen, J., Carugati, L., Cochrane, S., Danovaro, R., Heiskanen, A.-S., Karvinen, V., Moncheva, S., Murray, C., Neto, J., Nygård, H., Pantazi, M., Papadopoulou, N., Simboura, N., Srèbalienè, G., Uyarra, M., & Borja, A. (2016). Indicator-based

- assessment of marine biological diversity—lessons from 10 case studies across the European Seas. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 3, 159, 10.3389/fmars.2016.00159
- Van der Wilde, C. P., & Newell, J. P. (2021). Ecosystem services and life cycle assessment: A bibliometric review. *Resources Conservation and Recycling*, 169, 105461. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105461>
- Vázquez-Rowe, I., Moreira, M. T., & Feijoo, G. (2012). Inclusion of discard assessment indicators in fisheries life cycle assessment studies. Expanding the use of fishery-specific impact categories. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, 17(5), 535–549. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-012-0395-x>
- Vierros, M. (2013). Communities and blue carbon: the role of traditional management systems in providing benefits for carbon storage, biodiversity conservation and livelihoods. *Climatic Change*, 140(1), 89–100. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-013-0920-3>
- Wasmund, N., Kownacka, J., Göbel, J., Jaanus, A., Johansen, M., Jurgensone, I., Letinen, S. & Powilleit, M. (2017). The diatom/dinoflagellate index as an indicator of ecosystem changes in the Baltic Sea 1. Principle and handling instruction. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 4, 22, 10.3389/fmars.2017.00022.
- Waycott, M., Duarte, C. M., Carruthers, T. J. B., Orth, R. J., Dennison, W. C., Olyarnik, S., Calladine, A., Fourqurean, J. W., Heck, K. L., Hughes, A. R., Kendrick, G. A., Kenworthy, W. J., Short, F. T., & Williams, S. L. (2009). Accelerating loss of seagrasses across the globe threatens coastal ecosystems. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 106(30), 12377–12381. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0905620106>
- Wawrzynkowski, P., Molins, C., & Lloret, J. (2025). Assessing the potential impacts of floating Offshore Wind Farms on policy-relevant species: A case study in the Gulf of Roses, NW Mediterranean. *Marine Policy*, 172, 106518, 10.1016/j.marpol.2024.106518.
- Woods, J. S., & Verones, F. (2018). Ecosystem damage from anthropogenic seabed disturbance: A life cycle impact assessment characterization model. *The Science of the Total Environment*, 649, 1481–1490. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.08.304>

Zhang, Y., Zhao, M., Cui, Q., Fan, W., Qi, J., Chen, Y., Zhang, Y., Gao, K., Fan, J., Wang, G., Yan, C., Lu, H., Luo, Y., Zhang, Z., Zheng, Q., Xiao, W., & Jiao, N. (2017). Processes of coastal ecosystem carbon sequestration and approaches for increasing carbon sink. *Science China Earth Sciences*, *60*(5), 809–820. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11430-016-9010-9>

Zimmermann, J., Champagne, L. E., Dickens, J. M., & Hazen, B. T. (2024). Approaches to improve preprocessing for Latent Dirichlet Allocation topic modeling. *Decision Support Systems*, *185*, 114310. [10.1016/j.dss.2024.114310](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2024.114310)

MOIRAI

This report is made under the project
Multiscale Ocean models and Information for climate Risk Assessment and Impact
mitigation (MOIRAI).

Funded by
the European Union

Project partners:

